

"What It Is, Not What It Ain't! Escalating Tensions in the Mexican Drug War" by Brian Paul Kaess¹

I was experiencing balmy days in late Summer 2025 when things in Mexico apparently 'took a turn for the worse,' & the Mexican Drug War entered a critical, more dangerous phase. The cartels, long recalcitrant towards any type of control from their own government, and wielding significant power globally, had created a situation, through the *opiod* epidemic up north, where their continued operations were viewed menacingly in Washington. Within Mexico, during the drug war, homicides linked directly or indirectly to organized crime factions, fragmented cartel turf wars, and associated violence have resulted in a *gwestimated* figure of 350,000-400,000 deaths².

The author of this paper himself was present in San Jose de Ramos, Dgo., Mexico in 2007, unwittingly witnessing the Mexican Army burning bushels of *marijuana* in the streets of Ramos during a raid- which must have been one of the opening *salvos* of President Felipe Calderon's *Operation Michoacan*, an effort to eliminate drug plantations and target leadership. At the time in Ramos, my wife Mayte was scared, stating: 'the cartels can come here and kill us!' These raids into Ramos continued into 2010 & 2011, but pretty much ceased after that, to the best of my knowledge. And then gradually- just as before- the cartels went back to their old ways.

Even after authorities arrested stooge after stooge, any *vacuum* in cartel leadership was like the 'head of a hydra' that simply replenished itself. So there was a chaos or danger that was likely to evolve and perhaps even multiply, as the cartels themselves 'raged equal to mars.'³ Yet, the intransigence of the cartels to warnings from up north was on the cusp of collapse. With heightened rhetoric coming out of Washington, they could no longer ignore the admonitions. Trump may have seen a push against the cartels as long overdue, 'a day late and a dollar short,' as one might add. But ironically, they probably aren't sending 'Gringo' soldiers into Mexico to burn the cash!

Some even decided to stop shipping *fentanyl* across the border altogether and 'diversify.' The MORENA party, with its emphasis on socialism and 'feeding the people,' might even cause one to label Mexico a 'cheesy Dialectic.' Even though both AMLO and Sheinbaum had embraced a 'hugs, not bullits' policy for some time, Sheinbaum had to eventually 'pay the piper,' 'ante up' to Trump and start handing over drugs lords. High-level politicians, who may have lived in some sort of state 'enlightened ignorance' about the cartels for a time, mostly due to not wanting to stir the shark tank, so to speak, may have finally realized that action could no longer be delayed, and simply said to themselves with regard to the cartels: 'Don't worry, they're expendable,' *a la* the film, '*the Dogs of War* (1980),' With '*Trumpian* enthusiasm,' they reached a consensus that it was high time to tackle the drug cartels.

¹ It should be noted that the 'History,' 'Miscellany,' & 'Tensions,' all written by Brian Paul Kaess in 2025, may refer to something less than a *Tolkienesque*-style trilogy since they are bits and pieces of the same story, but nevertheless do not cover a secondary world so to speak, layered with fantastic elements, but find their setting in the actual world at large. The 'Tensions' is the 3rd of the trilogy and was completed on the eve of any potential American strike in Mexico.

² See 'Mexican drug war' at *Wikipedia.org* at https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mexican_drug_war

³ See Aelian *Varia Historia* p. 37.

Some of the drug cartels in Mexico that have been designated Foreign Terrorist Organizations (FTO's) by the USA include: *Cártel de Sinaloa*, *Cártel de Jalisco Nueva Generación (CJNG)*, *Cártel del Noreste* (formerly part of Los Zetas), *Cártel del Golfo* (Gulf Cartel), *La Nueva Familia Michoacana*, *Cárteles Unidos* (an alliance of several criminal groups).

Although the cartels listed above control or influence vast swathes of Mexican territory, my experience has shown me that Mexico is not actually a failed state, as some have claimed, but operates perhaps as a narco-influenced one. Transportation, agriculture, construction, tourism, energy, telecommunications, health care, & academia, are all in a robust mode and it is not unfair to describe these days in Mexico as 'boom times.' Such a state of affairs is the *antithesis* of a failed state. Therefore, it is clearly an exaggeration to say that Mexico is some sort of administrative 'desert.'

Minor cartels also play a significant, *albeit* understated, role in the Mexican Drug Scene. Mentioned here are but a few: Los Rojos, Los Ardillos, La Barredora, Los Granados, Los Viagras, El Cartel del Abuelo, Los Correa, Los Talibanes, Los Zetas Vieja Escuela, Cartel Independiente de Acapulco (CIDA), La Línea & Los Salazar. One minor cartel, which I have known as the Ramos-San Carlos Cartel, operating in El Oro, Durango is reportedly part of the Los Cabrera Sarabia⁴ criminal network, focused on drug trafficking routes through the *Sierra Madre Occidental*, with influence over local politics and law enforcement. This group is a regional cell aligned with the Sinaloa Cartel, specifically loyal to Ismael "El Mayo" Zambada. Los Cabrera Sarabia has deep roots in Durango and is considered one of the most entrenched factions in the "Triángulo Dorado" or 'Golden Triangle' - the mountainous drug-producing region spanning Durango, Sinaloa, and Chihuahua.

While not as internationally recognized as CJNG or Los Chapitos⁵, Los Cabrera Sarabia wields significant local influence, often operating through family-based networks and maintaining control over strategic municipalities like El Oro through alliances with local officials and law enforcement. Apparently, based on a newspaper account I have read, they primarily traffic *marijuana* and *heroin* to *el Norte*. It is said they like to drive dark, black SUV's when they deliver their wares. The many *circuitous* and winding mountain paths in El Oro, many of which I have taken myself heading into Ramos, offer ample opportunity to skirt the law.

News reports in the past decade have also highlighted Durango state as an important trans-shipment point for *metamphetamines*, with arrests increasing in recent years. There have been multiple operations and seizures in this regard- these stories being among some of the most conspicuous in local news and print media. There are not only military checkpoints in Durango, but occasional police ones as well. One time, the *policia municipal* helped us fix our vehicle, when it broke down late at night. We didn't even need a mechanic!

⁴ See story at *Emeequis.com* at <https://emeequis.com/al-dia/ellos-son-los-cabrera-sarabia-la-familia-criminal-ligada-a-un-senador-de-morena-y-al-cartel-de-sinaloa/>

⁵ See article in *Milenio* at <https://www.milenio.com/policia/narcotrafico/chapitos-mayos-guerra-cartel-sinaloa-afecta-otros-estados>

Also, "El Mayito Flaco" is the *alias* of Ismael Zambada Sicaños, the son of Ismael "El Mayo" Zambada, one of the longtime leaders of the Sinaloa Cartel. While his father is a legendary figure in the world of Mexican organized crime, El Mayito Flaco has emerged as a key operator in Durango, especially within the faction known as La Mayiza, which remains loyal to El Mayo's legacy. So, in modern drug war-torn Mexico, there are more cartels than butterflies!

Lupe, my wife's cousin, is said to have borne a child by a reputed Sinaloa cartel member. She keeps his photo—black hat and all—on her dresser as a reminder to herself and her son, Rafael Monarrez, perhaps because the father is seldom present. He is believed to spend significant time in the mountainous areas of Sinaloa. She is rumored to be a member of the Ramos-San Carlos Cartel, but she has always been pleasant to me, never mentioning drugs and even offering me water on one occasion, as hospitality would suggest. It is believed Lupe is related to Mayte on the Monarrez side, both having relations to Mayte's grandmother Leonila Barra Monarez (1915-2009), who was raised during the Mexican Revolution.

Lupe has worked at the largest mini-mart in Ramos, as a police officer, and opened her own dry-goods business with help from state subsidies. She has also lived in Kansas up north. She lives in a modest home at the edge of town in Ramos with her mom and son and sports a brown Dodge Durango as a ride. Her son was named after her brother Rafael, who has been instrumental in the child's care. Her house is just down the road from Braulio's homestead, who I have witnessed climb upon the roof to fix the satellite antenna!

Judy's ex-boyfriend, Willi, once a starving artist trained in Mexico City, has transitioned to a police captain in Durango in recent years and now has a new wife and child. He and Judy once invited me to go to a shooting range when I lived in Durango City, and even showed me images of an AR-15 as well as a vintage M-1. Braulio keeps his own 'stash' of weapons buried in the desert somewhere. It is strictly illegal to own firearms as a civilian in Mexico, but tell that to the horde of Mexicans who fire off their pistols 'Pancho-Villa'-style on New Year's.

Such was the issue with the 'Marine in Mexico' story in 2014 on CNN⁶ when U.S. Marine Reserve Sgt. Andrew Tamooressi, an Afghan War veteran, crossed the border with a number of weapons with no criminal intent, and yet, was possibly facing five years in prison. We are happy Greta Van Susteren took up his cause and later he was released by a Mexican judge after seven months confinement based on humanitarian grounds.

Another frightening event was the *Morelia grenade attacks* in 2008, when a couple of grenades were thrown into a crowd, while the governor was giving a speech hailing the *Grito de Independencia* on Mexican Independence Day, killing eight people. Watching the news of this event on TV presented an eerie feeling about the rising levels of strife, and marked a *chilling* escalation in the drug war. I remember hearing gunshots now and then at night when I lived in the *Barrio Tierra Blanca*, and some seemingly just a block away. Such are the frightful times we live in when the sounds of violence seem so *pedestrian* and commonplace.

⁶ See CNN story on May 29, 2014 at <https://www.foxnews.com/us/marine-sergeant-jailed-in-mexico-on-gun-charges-speaks-exclusively-on-the-record?msocid=1dad20aa043961401bb5319b05786055>

As *Newsweek* reported on Sept. 2, 2025, Marco Rubio, speaking to reporters before boarding his plane for a diplomatic visit to Mexico and Ecuador, said Trump "is going to be on offense against drug cartels and drug trafficking in the United States. It destabilizes not just the country but the entire Caribbean basin." He continued, "The president has been very clear that he's going to use the full power of America and the full might of the United States to take on and eradicate these drug cartels, no matter where they're operating from and no matter how long they've been able to act with impunity. Those days are over." It makes one want to listen to the heralded Johnny Cash song, 'When the Man Comes Around.'⁷

It reminds one of Mike Flynn's⁸ statement in his early days as National Security Advisor, when he said that 'As of today we are officially putting Iran on notice,' but in our present case, Rubio is speaking of the cartels in Latin America. If these official statements don't sound like a 'harbinger of doom,' I don't know what does!

Perhaps Trump will tickle the Right Wing base in his party in much the same way *Maximus of Ephesus* of antiquity did to his students when he caused the statue of *Hecate* to smile and laugh and prevailed upon the torches in her hands to burst into flames- black magic and philosophy combined!⁹

Also, it appears Trump may be going after cartels in Mexico and Venezuela at roughly the same time, and as the campaigns may be linked or staggered, we will mention U.S. assets sent off the coast of Venezuela first. Cartel activity in Mexico and the rest of Latin America appear to be two sides of the same dubious coin. Some of these cartels, such as Tren de Agua, have only recently been formed, and are thus of *embryonic* origin. While the region's fate hangs in the balance, we can only pray for a *serendipitous* outcome.

Pegged for the Venezuelan campaign are 9 U.S. warships¹⁰ including the following:

- * USS Gravelly, the following three are Arleigh Burke-class guided missile destroyers. These carry a Tomahawk cruise missile strike package.
- * USS Jason Dunham
- * USS Sampson
- * USS Iwo Jima, the next three are part of the Iwo Jima Amphibious Ready Group and carry more than 2,500 U.S. Marines of the 22nd MEU (Marine Expeditionary Unit) among them. Osprey aircraft are also aboard the Iwo Jima.
- * USS San Antonio
- * USS Fort Lauderdale
- * USS Lake Erie, is a a Ticonderoga-class guided-missile cruiser.
- * USS Minneapolis-Saint Paul, is a Freedom-class littoral combat ship.
- * USS Newport News, a Los Angeles-class nuclear-powered fast-attack submarine. It

⁷ See Johnny Cash 'When the Man Comes Around,' at *You Tube* video: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=k9IfHDi-2EA&start_radio=1

⁸ See *C-Span* of February 1, 2017 at <https://www.c-span.org/clip/white-house-event/national-security-adviser-michael-flynn-puts-iran-on-notice-after-missile-test/4654237>

⁹ See Eunapius, *Lives of the Philosophers and Sophists* (1921) pp.435-6.

¹⁰ See *Newsweek* story: <https://www.newsweek.com/list-us-navy-ships-venezuela-trump-maduro-2123734>

possesses a stealth dimension and also carries a Tomahawk land attack missiles. It carries Harpoon anti-ship missiles and Mark 48 torpedoes for potential interdiction of surface ships.

U.S. Naval Air and Coast Guard Assets, based out of Puerto Rico, include the Navy's P-8A Poseidon maritime patrol aircraft—designed for anti-submarine warfare & supplemented by P-3 Orion patrol planes used by U.S. Customs and Border Protection (CBP), as well as MQ-9 Reaper drones and F/A-18 Hornets. I wonder if these are from the U.S. Naval Base at Roosevelt Roads which I almost visited when I took leave as a U.S. Marine in Cuba back in the day.

What are the *objectives* of such an operation? First, at a minimum it provides a show of force in the hopes of convincing Maduro to change course. Second, it provides viable military, strike options to go after cartels and criminal gangs that were recently designated as terrorist organizations. Third, it provides options to strike at the Maduro regime itself. Fourth, it provides *succor* and political coverage to Maduro's opponents, giving them a chance at a 'breathing space' as events unfold. As my Cuban-American friend Rafael Cabañin would state *laconically*: 'the forces are gathering.'

Will Maduro capitulate and take flight? It is difficult to believe so and perhaps just as likely as Trump welcoming refugees at our southern border! In any case, such an *amalgam* of forces appears to be the requisite number needed for at least a short-term victory. There seems to be no *portcullis*, in figurative terms, that Maduro possesses that could possibly check Trump's *hubris* or unbridled ambition.

Trump himself announced a strike on a Venezuelan 'drug runner' craft carrying Tren de Agua gang members, killing 11 of them¹¹. So the little, littoral war had begun with a dash of Homeric passion and is now expanding with support from Trinidad and Tobago, as the U.S. president sharpens his saber-rattling, carefully gathering his flotilla off the South American coast, while Venezuela remains unyielding. He must surely not have thought of them as 'the better angels of our natures,' as Lincoln once wrote.

From August 8 to August 19th, during *Operation Pacific Viper*¹², the U.S. Coast Guard, as announced by the Dept. of Homeland Security, made a number of interdictions of drug-carrying vessels, some laden with thousands of pounds of cocaine. The agency has hunted down, interdicted, and boarded several illegal vessels, resulting in seizures and arrests. Some craft were set ablaze and others left to sink. Other vessels were shot at to disable their engine. There is even a video circulating online of one vessel being 'lit up.' Also apprehended were suspects & plenty of contraband. Mission accomplished right? Sounds like a small victory *amid* a sea of smugglers eager to reach our shores. If Lincoln could blockade southern ports, why can't Trump do the same to the drug smugglers? He sure is getting mighty keen about it.

¹¹ See *Newsweek* article: <https://www.msn.com/en-us/news/world/donald-trump-%20announces-military-strike-on-ship-departing-venezuela/ar-AA1LJzO>

¹² See *The Maritime Executive* of August 22, 2025 at <https://maritime-executive.com/article/u-s-seizes-13-000-pounds-of-cocaine-in-operation-pacific-viper>

Furthermore, the U.S. State Department announced on September 4, 2025¹³, that Secretary Rubio has designated Los Choneros and Los Lobos, of Ecuador, as FTO's and SDGTs. They are linked to the Sinaloa Cartel and *Cártel de Jalisco Nueva Generación* (CJNG), the virtual 'big boys' of the Mexican drug scene. Their ultimate goal is to control drug trafficking routes through Ecuador, never mindful of the misery they inflict on the populace. Ironically, *Lobos* is a popular mascot name for my wife Mayte's *alma mater*, UJED- but, oh how we are on different sides of the playing field!

The vast reach of the Mexican drug cartels shows how long the arms of this *strange octopus* extend across the globe. With suppliers from China to South America, never-declining demand in North America and Europe, trans-shipment points that cross the heart of Africa and the straits of Gibraltar, and a rampant cartel-friendly culture ever since *Scarface* (1983) that is reflected in film, the cartels remain poised to handle business as usual, pay to play, and use muscle when necessary.

One wonders, despite his *bellicose* rhetoric, if Trump actually believes he can eradicate or stamp out the cartels *en toto*, or simply put a dent in their pride. A belief in victory over the cartels may simply be a *chimera*- a goal too difficult to achieve, yet ever longed for. Does Trump really believe he can 'put the genie back into the bottle,' as one might describe the drug problem?

One wonders, as Trump becomes more *rapacious* and 'grasps for more' in Latin America, if this means he will stop at only interdiction/temporary intervention and not go for more, such as *de facto* annexation of some areas (oil-producing) in South America. His overall project of American expansionism might find 'fertile soil' there. For now, the situation retains a certain fluidity.

A bit farther away, in Mexico, storm clouds had been gathering for some time¹⁴, as lightning was striking elsewhere. With *impeccable* timing, the U.S. Military engaged a single target in the Caribbean Sea, and now it was just a matter of time before Mexico felt the same wrath too. The atmosphere was becoming ripe with suspense.

These incursions remind one of the Punitive Expedition¹⁵ by the U.S. Army in 1916 to capture Mexican Revolutionary Pancho Villa and prevent any further raids by his para-military forces along the borderlands. These *forays* into Mexican territory were eventually stalled, when Constitutionalist forces sent by Carranza in April, 1916, 'literally riding to Villa's rescue,' successfully countered Pershing's forces near Parral, and caused a halt, thus saving the Mexican state of Durango from a triumphant entry by the U.S. Army.

Thereafter, there was an ensuing dialogue between the two governments until the end of hostilities. The attempt to capture Villa had failed, but this may not be the case with many a drug lord in present-day Mexico!

¹³ See U.S. State Department announcement at <https://www.state.gov/releases/office-of-the-spokesperson/2025/09/terrorist-designations-of-los-choneros-and-los-lobos/>

¹⁴ Previous rising tensions in the Mexican Drug War have been discussed in *Kaess Miscellany: A Chronicle from 2025 Onwards* (2025) by Brian Paul Kaess.

¹⁵ See 'Pancho Villa Expedition' at *Wikipedia.org* at https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pancho_Villa_Expedition

In Las Villas, on Sept. 6, 2025¹⁶, I saw a news story on AOL where Mexican Independence Day celebrations in Chicago's Pilsen neighborhood turned into a veritable 'ghost town' because of ICE fears. Mayte's cousin Erlin used to work in Pilsen. Jewel-bedecked *folklorico* dancers distributed 'know your rights' pamphlets to the anxious and *sparce* crowd. Tensions were high as Trump promised to ramp up deportations- hopefully my family members won't be among them! Trump alluded to immigration raids in Chicago in a Truth Social post that echoed the movie *Apocalypse Now*. "I love the smell of deportations in the morning," his post said, above an image of Trump in a military uniform juxtaposed against flames and Chicago's skyline. "Chicago is about to find out why it's called the Department of WAR."

With the arrival of federal agents in sanctuary cities, an *adventus* of fear has gripped the land. Perhaps it may be that the term 'jack-booted government thug,' once used by Wayne LaPierre of the NRA in a fund-raising letter (in 1995), will re-emerge. There is little doubt that rhetoric is being dialed up amid fears of militarized policing. One wonders whether Trump, more aggressively pursuing his policy objectives during his 2nd term, will *morph* into something roughly *akin* to the Second Triumvirate, issuing his own brand of *proscriptions* when signing a *plethora* of executive orders. Let us hope, nonetheless, that out of this general *ferment*, a lasting peace can still prevail. One thing is for certain- Americans could use his help abroad.

Living free and easy myself in Mexico for some time, I managed to carve out for myself a semi-obscure existence. In fact, I've been living in Mexico for so long that I must be 'all grit & comfort' by now. I could actually care less about drugs, but the prevalence and persistence of the drug war within the borders of Mexico and across the region of North America was becoming an abiding concern for many, since its 'spillover' effect was not insignificant. Few in Mexico were disaffected by these events. We pray that things become better, lest Mexico dissolve into 'a river of grief.'

So, I was embracing an easy-going *hedonism*, and no one could've ever accused me of living in the style of the largesse of Aristotle, whom the *peripatetics* once accused of criticizing Plato in his old age, donning rich garments, and wearing more rings upon his fingers than Liberace himself- moderation my ass!

In any case, to keep faith with 'the spirit of the times,' I began listening to *Reggaetón*¹⁷, a Latin musical *genre* that has exploded upon the airwaves, suggesting a renewal and rebirth of my own musical taste. It was time to feel the pulse. After watching some of these videos, you'd think 'pink cocaine' was going to hit the streets! At least the *genre* has awakened in me a long dormant *aesthetic*. I was hoping to stay upbeat about the possibility of decreased tensions amid the current geopolitical situation.

The following videos shown below struck a particular chord:

¹⁶ See AOL news story: 'Chicago protesters defiant in face of Trump's deportation threats' <https://www.aol.com/news/chicago-ice-fears-turn-mexican-195416734.html>

¹⁷ See 'Regaetton' in *Britannica* at <https://www.britannica.com/art/reggaeton>

1. Ozuna Que Va
2. "Brickell" - Feid, Yandel 150
3. Ozuna x J Balvin x Chenzo Corleone - Una Locura
4. Bad Bunny x Jhay Cortez - DÁKITI
5. Wisin - Escápate Conmigo (Official Video) ft. Ozuna
6. Ozuna - DEPRIMIDA
7. Ozuna- Caramelo
8. Becky G, Bad Bunny - Mayores
9. Yomil y El Dany - Te paso a buscar (Live Cecilia)

A favorite and home-grown genre of music in Durango state is *Banda*¹⁸, sometimes tied to *narcocorridos*. The connection between *Banda* music and the drug scene-particularly in northern Mexico-is complex, layered, and often misunderstood. If *Banda* is the chicken, then *narcocorridos* is the egg! While *Banda* itself is a traditional genre rooted in brass instrumentation and regional storytelling, a subgenre known as *narcocorridos* has created a controversial bridge between music and drug culture.

So, while *Banda* and *narcocorridos* sometimes overlap, there are significant differences:

* *Banda* music: Originates from rural Mexico, especially Sinaloa and Durango. *Sinaloa Banda* was shaped by German and Spanish immigrants who brought brass instruments and musical styles like polkas, waltzes, and marches. It's festive, emotional, and often celebrates love, heartbreak, and local pride.

* *Narcocorridos*: A modern evolution of the traditional corrido, these songs narrate the lives of drug traffickers, glorify cartel figures, and detail violent events or criminal exploits. In defense of their style, one can say they are a cultural reflection, not promotion. Yet, *narcocorridos* often portray traffickers as folk heroes-rising from poverty to power, much like gangsta rap in the U.S.; Some artists have been pressured to write songs that favor certain factions or cartels. Some artists have even been targeted themselves.

Below are a number of top *Banda* songs that I have probably heard once or twice at holiday parties or listening to outdoors *Banda* bands in El Pueblito. My joke is, if you're good, you listen to *Banda*, and if you're bad, you listen to the other type of music (*narcocorridos*). Although *narcocorridos* have been banned in parts of Mexico and the U.S., their popularity and resonance with the public cannot be denied.

On the following page is the *Banda* list:

¹⁸ See MA Thesis by Kristen L. Richmond 'Corridos, Drugs, and Violence: An Analysis of Mexican Drug Ballads' at <https://researchrepository.wvu.edu/etd/7344/>

1. Paraiso Tropical de Durango - "Soy Duranguense"
2. Patrulla 81 - "Pantalón Vaquero"
3. Banda La Recia - "El De Durango"
4. Banda MS - "El Amor De Su Vida"
5. Ariel Camacho y Los Plebes del Rancho- "Te Metiste"
6. Banda El Recodo- "Hermosa Experiencia"
7. La Arrolladora Banda El Limón- "Y Lloro"
8. Banda MS- "Mi Razón De Ser"
9. Christian Nodal (Duranguense crossover hit)- "Adiós Amor"

Don't worry, there is plenty of *Banda* bands/music left to choose from in the Durango area¹⁹. Also, another pick here. I noticed Perfecta being played on occasion by construction workers in my development at Las Villas, and it is an excellent representative of the type of music played in Mexico in these times.

Here goes:

- * Perfecta (Video Oficial) - Los Alameños De La Sierra²⁰

This one, fashioned up north, will keep you on your toes. You could almost mistake it for white, gangsta rap:

- * Maxx- Get Away (Official Video)²¹

Then there is an upbeat trance song that reflects the spirit of the times we live in:

- * Trance tecnológico de resonancia fría de F3RN1DJ²²

This final one hails philosophy as a key, something I can relate to:

- * INFINITY (REMIX) - GURU JOSH PROJECT - Braian Leiva²³

Trump, with typical arrogance, has been attempting to end birthright citizenship, embolden mass deportations, embrace QAnon-conspiracy theories, and displays a 'cult of personality' not unlike Joseph Stalin- and literally shows signs of a man with 'no trace of the common touch.' QAnon is a far-right conspiracy theory claiming that Trump is secretly fighting a global *cabal* of Satan-worshipping pedophiles embedded in government, media, and business. Whether this is true or not, he is the American leader who is prepared to launch strikes into Latin America, and hence change the dynamic, vector & direction of the War on Drugs.

¹⁹ For the latest on the Durango music scene, see *Música Durango*

<https://www.last.fm/es/tag/durango/artists>

²⁰ See *you tube* video:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kOD7w41LUwE&list=RDkOD7w41LUwE&start_radio=1

²¹ See *you tube* video:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7uhWJATdXMA&list=RD7uhWJATdXMA&start_radio=1

²² See *you tube* video: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=34-ZJeJ1QwQ&list=RD34-ZJeJ1QwQ&start_radio=1

²³ See *you tube* video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rFBYfs5xMDc&list=RD34-ZJeJ1QwQ&index=5>

(Below Image: President Donald Trump, 45th & 47th U.S. President with entourage including Jeffrey Epstein.)

(Above Image: guided-missile destroyer USS Sampson sails near the Colombian coast in the Pacific Ocean on June 29, 2024²⁴. The Sampson and other US vessels are now gathered in the Caribbean Sea off the coast of Venezuela, poised to strike the drug cartels.)

(Above Image: USCG destroyed smugglers' boats and seized cocaine as part of *Operation Pacific Viper*, photo courtesy of USCG)

²⁴ Image from *Washington Post* article of August 27, 2025 at <https://www.washingtonpost.com/national-security/2025/08/27/us-warships-venezuela-maduro-trump/>

(Above Image: Brian Paul Kaess, *circa* September 2025, sitting on the front lawn of his wife Mayte's house in Las Villas, Durango, Mexico. His wife Mayte took the photo. This image was snapped around the time of some of these events that I have mentioned in this paper. Brian looks ready for some informal, rustic conversation, Thoreau-style—and indeed, it is true that Las Villas has the feel of being somewhere out “in the boonies.” The author, with typical flair, has dubbed himself the ‘Ayatollah of Smackola!’)

Brian Kaess